

A challenge to “Spatial disparities in the mortality burden of the covid-19 pandemic across 569 European regions (2020-2021)”

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In their paper, Bonnet et al. [1] have calculated the regional distribution of excess mortality in Europe for the years 2020 and 2021. They presented their results in terms of age-standardised years of life lost (ASYLL) and changes in life expectancy (LE), which they compared [1, suppl. app., tab. 2] to those of another recent study [2]. However, Modig et al. [3] not long ago suggested “that basic mortality rates should be presented alongside summary measures whenever possible to guide the readers” [3]. We fully agree. In a recent study [4], we have estimated all-cause excess mortality between 2020 and 2022 for whole Germany, by applying a different technique (see a concise description in the legend of our Fig. 1). Moreover, we have demonstrated that extrapolation through splines – the methodical basis in [1] (see also [5]) – is prone to errors. In particular, we showed that three different forecasts (prognoses) by WHO-endorsed models [6, 7], two of them based on spline extrapolations, significantly deviated in the years 2020 and 2021 from both the observed all-cause mortality counts of the entire German population [4, app. C, fig. 9] (resulting in exaggerated excess mortality estimates) and the respective counts estimated by any of our two model versions [4, sec. 2.3, sec. 3.2, fig. 4]. Accordingly, we challenge the authors of [1] to present to the readers of *Nature Communications* the plain values of their forecast (prognosticated, expected) death counts for whole Germany. This forecast should ideally comprise the years 2020 to 2023, including mean values and credibility intervals – similar to our Table 1. By this means, the model would prove its reliability, building confidence in the methodology of CP-spline-based forecasting.

Fig. 1 Comparison of all-cause mortality counts (AMCs) in German from 2000 to 2023. Black dots are numbers observed by the German bureau of statistics (*Destatis*), green marks (with bars giving confidence intervals, CIs) are corresponding, expected point estimates calculated by the ‘exponential’ model explained in [4]. This model is based on least-squares fitting of a two-parameter, continuously decreasing exponential function to each age cohort’s time course of its annual values of size-normalised all-cause mortality rate (AMR) from 2000 through 2019 (vertical grey line symbolises end of fitting period). For any year, the expected values of all these cohort’s normalised AMRs are weighted by the correspondingly observed values of the cohorts’ sizes (demography) to calculate the expected AMC of the whole population. Expected deaths from 2020 on are gained by extrapolating all cohorts’ exponential AMR functions. Also shown are three versions of WHO-endorsed calculations (red marks).

Table 1 Observed annual AMCs of the whole German population for the years 2020-2023, as well as point estimates by our ‘exponential’ expectation model. The difference between the observed and the expected AMC, i.e. the mean excess mortality count, and the corresponding 90% CI radii from our model calculations are given in the last two columns. Significant excess mortality in 2022 is marked with an asterisk (*).

year	deaths	deaths	excess deaths	
	(observed)	(modelled)	mean	CI radius
2020	985,572	1,004,043	-18,471	37,561
2021	1,023,687	1,016,695	6,992	38,855
2022	1,066,341	1,022,874	43,467*	39,423
2023	1,027,916	1,028,893	-951	39,980

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Statements & Declarations

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Competing Interests

We have no conflicts of interest.

Submission history

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